

Performance Evaluation of Deep Learning Architectures for Tree Branch Segmentation in Autonomous Forestry Systems

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Abstract—Tree branch segmentation supports autonomous forestry operations such as UAV navigation and automated pruning. We evaluate deep learning architectures at three resolutions (256×256, 512×512, 1024×1024) using the Urban Street Tree Dataset. We assess performance using standard metrics (IoU, Dice) and domain-specific measures including Thin Structure IoU (TS-IoU) for fine-branch detection and Connectivity Preservation Rate (CPR) for topology preservation. Among 22 configurations tested, U-Net with MiT-B4 backbone achieves strong performance at 256×256 across multiple metrics. At 512×512, MiT-B4 leads in IoU, Dice, TS-IoU, and Boundary-F1. At 1024×1024, U-Net+MiT-B3 shows the best validation performance for IoU/Dice and precision, while boundary quality is best with U-Net++. PSPNet provides the most efficient option (2.36/9.43/37.74 GFLOPs) with reduced accuracy. These results provide multi-resolution benchmarks for accuracy–efficiency trade-offs in forestry applications. Implementation is available at https://github.com/BennyLinntu/Performance_Tree_Branch_Segmentation.

Index Terms—Tree branch segmentation, semantic segmentation, UAV applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Autonomous forestry operations have potential to improve worker safety and operational efficiency in tree maintenance tasks. Manual pruning operations require workers to operate at heights, often near power lines, creating occupational risks. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) equipped with computer vision systems offer an alternative approach through automated branch identification and pruning operations [1].

Accurate branch segmentation is important for vision-guided forestry systems. Tree branches present challenges that distinguish them from objects in standard computer vision datasets. These structures exhibit high aspect ratios (often exceeding 100:1), occupy small image areas (typically less than 3% of total pixels), and form complex hierarchical patterns across multiple scales [2]. These characteristics differ from tasks in datasets such as COCO [3] or Cityscapes [4], which typically feature more balanced object distributions.

Real-world deployment introduces constraints beyond laboratory conditions. Autonomous forestry applications must handle variable lighting conditions, motion blur from UAV movement, diverse viewing angles, and complex backgrounds while maintaining performance on resource-constrained embedded platforms [5]. Safety requirements demand good precision—undetected branches pose operational risks, while false positives lead to unnecessary vegetation damage.

Current research in precision forestry focuses primarily on canopy-level analysis for species classification and health monitoring [6]. Individual branch segmentation remains relatively underexplored, particularly regarding embedded deployment requirements. Existing evaluation protocols rely predominantly on standard metrics that may inadequately capture the connectivity preservation and thin structure detection capabilities needed for structural analysis in forestry applications.

This work addresses these limitations through evaluation of deep learning architectures for branch segmentation at three input resolutions (256×256, 512×512, and 1024×1024). We assess segmentation heads and CNN/transformer backbones, introducing specialized evaluation metrics for thin structure analysis.

The main contributions of this research are:

- Performance evaluation of segmentation heads and backbones across 256×256, 512×512, and 1024×1024, analyzing accuracy–efficiency trade-offs (FLOPs)
- Two specialized evaluation metrics (TS-IoU, CPR) that complement IoU/Dice for thin-structure and topology assessment
- Benchmark across CNN and transformer backbones with consistent training and evaluation protocols
- Application-oriented guidance based on metric profiles and FLOPs for embedded selection

These contributions establish performance baselines and provide insights for computer vision applications in autonomous forestry.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Deep Learning for Semantic Segmentation

Semantic segmentation has evolved through several architectural paradigms. Encoder-decoder networks, pioneered by U-Net [8], employ symmetric architectures with skip connections to preserve spatial details during upsampling. Subsequent developments include U-Net++ [9], which introduces nested skip connections for improved feature propagation, Attention U-Net [10], which incorporates attention mechanisms for selective feature enhancement, and U-Net3+ [11], which implements full-scale feature aggregation.

The DeepLab series [12], [13] employs dilated convolution approaches to expand receptive fields without resolution

loss. DeepLabV3+ combines Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP) for multi-scale feature extraction with encoder-decoder refinement for boundary precision. PSPNet [14] utilizes spatial pyramid pooling for global context capture, though aggressive pooling may affect fine structure preservation.

Recent transformer-based approaches like Mask2Former [15] show improved performance on standard benchmarks but require substantial computational resources that may be challenging for embedded deployment.

B. Thin Structure Segmentation

Thin structure detection spans multiple application domains with varying technical challenges. Medical vessel segmentation shares structural similarities with branch detection, employing topology-preserving loss functions [16] and specialized attention mechanisms to maintain tubular connectivity. Infrastructure monitoring applications, including road network extraction [17] and crack detection [18], address similar geometric challenges but typically involve more predictable patterns and controlled imaging conditions.

Tree structure analysis remains limited in scope. Prior work [19] demonstrated branch detection for fruit trees in controlled orchard environments, while subsequent research [20] focused on crown delineation for species identification rather than detailed structural analysis. These studies do not address the complexity requirements of autonomous forestry applications in uncontrolled environments.

C. Computer Vision in Forestry Applications

Current UAV-based forestry applications emphasize large-scale monitoring rather than detailed structural analysis. Established applications include forest health assessment [21], species classification using deep learning [22], and biomass estimation [23]. However, most systems operate at canopy level using imagery insufficient for individual branch analysis.

Gaps exist between computer vision research and practical deployment requirements. Current evaluations predominantly use standard metrics that may be inadequate for forestry-specific requirements such as connectivity preservation and structural integrity assessment. Computational constraints receive limited consideration despite being important for autonomous system deployment.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Formulation

We formulate tree branch segmentation as a binary pixel classification problem. Each pixel p in input image $\mathcal{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3}$ is classified as either foreground (branch/trunk) or background. The segmentation network learns a mapping $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times 3} \rightarrow [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ parameterized by learnable weights θ . The final binary segmentation mask \mathcal{M} is obtained through thresholding: $\mathcal{M}(p) = \mathbb{I}[f_\theta(\mathcal{I})(p) > 0.5]$, where $\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ denotes the indicator function.

B. Dataset

We utilize the Urban Street Tree Dataset [7], containing 1,485 high-resolution images (3024×4032 pixels) with pixel-level branch annotations. The dataset provides characteristics suitable for forestry applications:

- **High Resolution:** Native image resolution of 3024×4032 pixels provides detail for fine branch structure analysis and supports multi-resolution evaluation
- **Species Diversity:** Thirteen different tree species enhance model generalization capabilities
- **Complex Backgrounds:** Natural urban environments with varying lighting conditions and occlusions mirror challenging conditions encountered in real-world forest deployments
- **Binary Annotation:** Each pixel is labeled as either branch/trunk or background, providing clear ground truth for binary classification

The dataset’s species diversity is valuable for developing segmentation models that can generalize across different tree morphologies. This characteristic may be useful for future applications in Radiata pine forests, where models trained on diverse urban species could demonstrate adaptability to new coniferous structures.

We employ a 60/20/20 train/validation/test split (891/297/297 images) stratified by tree species to ensure representative distribution across all evaluation phases.

C. Architecture Implementation

We evaluate segmentation heads and backbones representative of current approaches:

Segmentation heads: U-Net [8], U-Net++ [9], DeepLabV3 [12], DeepLabV3+ [13], FPN [24], PSPNet [14], LinkNet [25], and MAnet.

Backbones: ResNet34/50 [26], MobileNetV2 [27], DenseNet121 [28], EfficientNet-B0 [29], ConvNeXt-Base [30], and transformer-based backbones including ViT-B/16 [31], Swin-Base [32], LeViT-128s [33], and MiT-B0–B5 (SegFormer) [34].

All models are trained independently at each input resolution (256×256, 512×512, 1024×1024) using AdamW optimizer (weight decay 10^{-4}) with a base learning rate of 10^{-3} , cosine annealing over 200 epochs, and early stopping based on validation loss. The loss function combines Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) and Dice loss to address class imbalance:

$$\mathcal{L} = 0.3 \cdot \mathcal{L}_{BCE} + 0.7 \cdot \mathcal{L}_{Dice} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{L}_{BCE} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)] \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{Dice} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \hat{y}_i + \epsilon}{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i + \sum_{i=1}^N \hat{y}_i + \epsilon} \quad (3)$$

The weighting emphasizes Dice loss for overlap quality while maintaining gradient stability through BCE inclusion.

Fig. 1: Example RGB images and ground-truth branch masks from the Urban Street Tree Dataset [7].

D. Evaluation Metrics

Standard segmentation metrics may be insufficient for thin structure evaluation due to class imbalance and topology considerations. We employ conventional, specialized, and auxiliary metrics to assess performance:

1) *Standard Metrics: Intersection over Union (IoU)*:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|Y \cap \hat{Y}|}{|Y \cup \hat{Y}|} \quad (4)$$

Dice Coefficient:

$$\text{Dice} = \frac{2|Y \cap \hat{Y}|}{|Y| + |\hat{Y}|} \quad (5)$$

where Y represents ground truth and \hat{Y} denotes predicted segmentation masks.

2) *Domain-Specific Metrics: Thin Structure IoU (TS-IoU)*: Standard IoU may inadequately assess thin structure performance due to minimal pixel contribution. TS-IoU computes IoU specifically for branches with width less than 5 pixels:

$$\text{TS-IoU} = \frac{|Y_{thin} \cap \hat{Y}_{thin}|}{|Y_{thin} \cup \hat{Y}_{thin}|} \quad (6)$$

where Y_{thin} represents ground truth pixels belonging to morphologically identified thin branches. This metric addresses the challenge that thin branches, despite minimal image coverage, are important for structural integrity and safety assessment.

Connectivity Preservation Rate (CPR): Traditional pixel-wise metrics ignore topological relationships important for branch analysis. CPR measures the percentage of ground truth connected components adequately preserved in predictions:

$$\text{CPR} = \frac{1}{N_{cc}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{cc}} \mathbb{I}[\text{IoU}(C_i, \hat{C}_i) > \tau] \quad (7)$$

where N_{cc} is the number of connected components in ground truth, C_i represents the i -th component, \hat{C}_i is the corresponding prediction region (identified via maximum overlap), and $\tau = 0.5$ is the preservation threshold. This metric is useful for autonomous systems requiring branch connectivity understanding for safe operation.

3) *Auxiliary Metrics: Boundary-F1*: F1-score computed between contour maps of ground-truth and predictions. Contours are obtained via morphological gradient; matches are assessed within a small tolerance to account for annotation uncertainty.

Skeleton Similarity: Dice coefficient computed between skeletonized ground-truth and predicted masks (morphological skeletonization), reflecting agreement on centerlines of thin structures.

4) *Evaluation Framework Rationale*: These complementary metrics address different aspects relevant for autonomous forestry:

- **Standard IoU/Dice**: Overall segmentation quality for general performance assessment
- **TS-IoU**: Targeted evaluation of fine branch detection relevant to safety applications
- **CPR**: Topological correctness useful for path planning and structural analysis

This framework addresses both pixel-level accuracy and structural properties relevant for real-world deployment, contrasting with standard benchmarks that emphasize overall accuracy without considering thin structure preservation requirements.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Overall Performance across Resolutions

Tables I–III present performance comparisons at 256×256, 512×512, and 1024×1024 resolutions. Results are reported as validation/test pairs across all metrics.

B. Performance Analysis

a) 256×256 (Table I): U-Net+MiT-B4 performs well overall, leading in IoU, Dice, Recall, TS-IoU, Boundary-F1, and Skeleton Similarity on validation and maintaining high performance on test data. Precision is highest with U-Net+MiT-B3 on both validation and test, whereas CPR is highest on test with U-Net+MiT-B5. PSPNet provides the lowest compute cost (2.36 GFLOPs) with reduced accuracy.

b) 512×512 (Table II): U-Net+MiT-B4 achieves good IoU and Dice performance on validation and test, along with strong TS-IoU and boundary quality metrics. U-Net+MiT-B3 yields high precision on validation and test (91.7%/91.3%), while U-Net+MiT-B5 achieves high recall on validation and

TABLE I: Performance Comparison at 256×256 Resolution (Validation/Test)

Methods	Backbone	IoU (%)	Dice (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	TS-IoU (%)	CPR (%)	Boundary-F1 (%)	Skeleton Similarity	FLOPs (G)
U-Net	ResNet34	65.1 / 65.0	77.8 / 77.8	79.6 / 80.3	77.2 / 76.5	67.4 / 67.9	36.4 / 37.0	27.1 / 27.6	19.1 / 20.1	7.85
U-Net++	ResNet34	69.1 / 69.6	80.9 / 81.3	82.5 / 83.8	80.3 / 79.7	71.6 / 72.5	38.2 / 42.9	35.8 / 36.4	26.0 / 26.9	18.45
DeepLabV3	ResNet34	54.9 / 54.4	69.3 / 68.9	70.5 / 70.9	69.6 / 68.6	59.4 / 59.4	34.2 / 35.2	11.4 / 11.7	7.6 / 7.5	27.351
DeepLabV3+	ResNet34	59.5 / 59.7	73.2 / 73.5	78.4 / 78.3	70.0 / 70.5	64.3 / 64.7	35.6 / 35.7	18.8 / 19.3	12.1 / 12.4	7.925
FPN	ResNet34	58.2 / 58.0	72.1 / 72.2	73.6 / 73.0	72.1 / 72.5	61.0 / 61.1	33.5 / 32.4	15.8 / 16.0	11.4 / 11.7	6.875
PSPNet	ResNet34	48.1 / 48.0	62.8 / 62.8	70.3 / 68.7	59.0 / 59.9	53.2 / 52.9	31.8 / 31.5	9.0 / 9.0	5.5 / 5.5	2.359
LinkNet	ResNet34	58.2 / 58.2	72.5 / 72.3	69.2 / 69.0	78.1 / 77.7	59.1 / 59.4	32.3 / 31.7	17.6 / 17.9	13.1 / 13.1	5.474
MAnet	ResNet34	63.2 / 63.1	76.4 / 76.4	78.3 / 78.8	75.6 / 75.0	65.0 / 65.7	35.1 / 33.3	23.7 / 24.2	17.4 / 17.9	8.355
U-Net	ResNet50	68.4 / 68.3	80.3 / 80.3	82.9 / 83.2	78.6 / 78.5	71.8 / 72.0	37.6 / 41.5	34.2 / 34.8	24.3 / 24.8	10.707
U-Net	MobileNetV2	62.4 / 63.0	75.7 / 76.2	77.6 / 77.6	75.1 / 76.0	63.7 / 65.0	32.4 / 34.8	25.7 / 25.9	18.6 / 18.7	3.396
U-Net	DenseNet121	67.2 / 67.9	79.4 / 80.0	82.6 / 83.2	77.4 / 77.9	69.8 / 70.7	36.2 / 39.1	32.7 / 33.3	23.4 / 24.2	8.489
U-Net	EfficientNet-B0	66.2 / 66.9	78.7 / 79.3	79.9 / 80.4	78.4 / 79.2	67.9 / 69.0	36.6 / 38.0	30.8 / 31.3	21.9 / 22.5	2.533
U-Net	ConvNeXt-Base	68.1 / 68.2	80.2 / 80.2	82.0 / 82.2	79.2 / 79.1	70.6 / 71.2	37.5 / 41.8	33.7 / 34.2	23.9 / 24.4	20.836
U-Net	ViT-B/16	65.1 / 64.8	77.8 / 77.6	80.2 / 80.2	76.6 / 76.2	67.5 / 67.4	35.9 / 37.8	26.7 / 27.1	19.7 / 19.9	4.625
U-Net	Swin-Base	65.1 / 64.8	77.8 / 77.6	80.4 / 80.4	76.4 / 76.2	67.7 / 67.5	35.7 / 37.6	27.2 / 27.5	19.9 / 20.0	15.845
U-Net	LeViT-128s	53.0 / 53.3	67.7 / 68.0	71.2 / 71.7	67.5 / 67.5	54.2 / 55.5	31.6 / 34.6	19.6 / 19.5	14.2 / 14.2	2.974
U-Net	MiT-B0	66.1 / 65.7	78.6 / 78.3	79.6 / 79.9	78.3 / 77.5	68.1 / 68.1	36.2 / 36.0	25.1 / 25.9	18.4 / 18.8	2.932
U-Net	MiT-B1	69.2 / 68.4	80.9 / 80.3	82.4 / 82.4	80.0 / 79.0	71.0 / 70.7	36.6 / 39.8	30.7 / 31.0	22.0 / 22.3	4.882
U-Net	MiT-B2	71.1 / 70.4	82.3 / 81.7	84.7 / 84.4	80.5 / 79.9	74.0 / 73.7	42.2 / 42.6	34.0 / 34.0	24.4 / 24.6	6.887
U-Net	MiT-B3	71.3 / 70.6	82.3 / 81.9	85.5 / 85.7	80.0 / 79.2	74.5 / 74.6	42.1 / 41.6	35.3 / 35.5	25.1 / 25.1	10.549
U-Net	MiT-B4	73.8 / 72.6	84.2 / 83.4	84.8 / 83.9	84.2 / 83.3	76.1 / 75.0	43.6 / 43.6	39.2 / 39.1	28.7 / 28.4	14.065
U-Net	MiT-B5	72.5 / 71.8	83.3 / 82.7	84.6 / 84.7	82.4 / 81.4	74.9 / 74.9	41.5 / 44.2	37.2 / 37.3	26.8 / 26.9	17.647

TABLE II: Performance Comparison at 512×512 Resolution (Validation/Test)

Methods	Backbone	IoU (%)	Dice (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	TS-IoU (%)	CPR (%)	Boundary-F1 (%)	Skeleton Similarity	FLOPs (G)
U-Net	ResNet34	77.9 / 77.4	87.1 / 86.7	87.7 / 87.6	86.9 / 86.4	79.8 / 79.3	24.4 / 24.3	34.1 / 34.1	26.6 / 26.6	31.40
U-Net++	ResNet34	80.2 / 79.5	88.6 / 88.2	89.5 / 89.3	88.1 / 87.6	82.2 / 81.5	29.0 / 26.9	38.9 / 38.9	29.9 / 30.1	73.80
DeepLabV3+	ResNet34	71.6 / 71.4	82.6 / 82.6	84.6 / 84.2	81.7 / 81.7	74.6 / 74.5	22.1 / 24.0	20.6 / 21.4	14.6 / 15.3	31.70
DeepLabV3	ResNet34	69.2 / 68.6	80.9 / 80.5	80.3 / 79.8	82.0 / 81.7	72.0 / 71.4	26.2 / 27.6	16.1 / 16.4	11.6 / 11.8	109.40
FPN	ResNet34	71.7 / 71.4	82.7 / 82.6	84.6 / 84.7	81.6 / 81.2	74.6 / 74.4	21.7 / 23.4	20.7 / 21.2	15.1 / 15.8	27.50
PSPNet	ResNet34	64.2 / 63.7	76.9 / 76.5	80.7 / 80.1	74.5 / 74.2	68.2 / 67.7	22.9 / 24.1	12.5 / 12.6	8.3 / 8.4	9.43
LinkNet	ResNet34	74.5 / 74.0	84.8 / 84.4	86.1 / 86.1	84.1 / 83.5	76.6 / 76.1	12.3 / 12.3	28.1 / 28.2	21.1 / 21.3	21.90
MAnet	ResNet34	77.0 / 76.8	86.4 / 86.3	86.9 / 86.6	86.7 / 86.7	78.6 / 78.4	25.8 / 26.7	33.1 / 33.4	25.5 / 25.8	33.42
U-Net	ResNet50	79.0 / 78.5	87.8 / 87.5	88.4 / 88.2	87.6 / 87.2	81.1 / 80.5	28.4 / 28.9	36.7 / 37.2	27.6 / 28.2	42.83
U-Net	MobileNetV2	76.2 / 75.4	85.8 / 85.3	86.7 / 86.3	85.8 / 85.4	78.1 / 77.1	19.5 / 18.3	32.9 / 32.8	24.8 / 24.9	13.58
U-Net	DenseNet121	78.5 / 78.5	87.5 / 87.5	88.2 / 88.3	87.2 / 87.3	80.2 / 80.1	21.5 / 23.3	36.5 / 36.8	28.0 / 28.7	33.96
U-Net	EfficientNet-B0	78.4 / 78.3	87.4 / 87.3	88.1 / 88.4	87.4 / 87.0	80.4 / 80.6	18.9 / 18.6	36.3 / 36.6	27.3 / 27.8	10.13
U-Net	ConvNeXt-Base	79.0 / 78.7	87.8 / 87.6	89.0 / 88.8	87.0 / 87.1	81.2 / 80.8	26.5 / 30.5	36.6 / 37.1	27.7 / 28.0	56.26
U-Net	ViT-B/16	77.8 / 77.0	87.0 / 86.4	87.8 / 87.5	86.7 / 85.9	79.7 / 79.1	26.4 / 25.2	34.1 / 34.1	26.4 / 26.6	27.55
U-Net	Swin-Base	77.9 / 77.3	87.1 / 86.7	87.5 / 87.2	87.2 / 86.7	79.6 / 79.2	25.2 / 26.1	34.4 / 34.4	26.8 / 26.8	56.26
U-Net	LeViT-128s	66.9 / 67.3	79.0 / 79.3	80.2 / 80.9	79.4 / 79.3	68.8 / 69.5	16.1 / 16.0	25.3 / 25.6	18.9 / 19.0	11.89
U-Net	MiT-B0	80.1 / 79.4	88.6 / 88.1	89.2 / 89.0	88.3 / 87.6	82.0 / 81.2	26.4 / 29.3	35.6 / 35.9	27.0 / 27.5	11.73
U-Net	MiT-B1	81.5 / 80.8	89.4 / 89.0	90.3 / 90.4	88.9 / 88.1	83.3 / 82.8	32.8 / 31.1	38.5 / 38.7	29.8 / 30.1	19.53
U-Net	MiT-B2	82.9 / 82.3	90.3 / 89.9	90.7 / 90.3	90.2 / 90.0	85.0 / 84.0	33.2 / 35.4	42.1 / 42.7	32.0 / 32.7	27.55
U-Net	MiT-B3	83.3 / 82.6	90.6 / 90.1	91.7 / 91.3	89.8 / 89.2	85.3 / 84.4	33.5 / 33.6	42.3 / 42.9	32.5 / 32.9	42.20
U-Net	MiT-B4	83.8 / 83.1	90.9 / 90.4	91.4 / 91.1	90.6 / 90.1	85.9 / 85.0	35.7 / 36.3	44.0 / 44.6	33.6 / 34.0	56.26
U-Net	MiT-B5	83.6 / 82.9	90.8 / 90.3	90.9 / 90.5	90.9 / 90.5	85.7 / 84.8	38.7 / 34.3	43.8 / 44.3	33.7 / 33.6	70.59

test (90.9%/90.5%) and good CPR on validation (38.7%). Test CPR is highest with MiT-B4 (36.3%). PSPNet again offers the lowest FLOPs (9.43G) with reduced accuracy.

c) 1024×1024 (Table III): U-Net+MiT-B3 provides good validation IoU/Dice and precision; U-Net+MiT-B4/B5

achieve strong test IoU/Dice performance, with recall being high with MiT-B4. Boundary quality (Boundary-F1) is best with U-Net++ on both validation and test, and Skeleton Similarity is highest on test with MiT-B4. FLOPs increase substantially at this scale; PSPNet remains the most efficient

TABLE III: Performance Comparison at 1024×1024 Resolution (Validation/Test)

Methods	Backbone	IoU (%)	Dice (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	TS-IoU (%)	CPR (%)	Boundary-F1 (%)	Skeleton Similarity	FLOPs (G)
U-Net	ResNet34	83.9 / 83.3	91.0 / 90.6	91.5 / 90.9	90.9 / 90.8	84.9 / 84.2	13.0 / 14.6	29.6 / 29.9	24.4 / 24.5	125.596
U-Net++	ResNet34	86.3 / 85.8	92.4 / 92.1	92.3 / 92.3	92.8 / 92.3	87.1 / 86.5	17.3 / 18.4	35.8 / 36.8	28.8 / 29.4	295.197
DeepLabV3	ResNet34	80.8 / 80.2	88.9 / 88.6	89.2 / 88.8	89.0 / 88.7	81.9 / 81.4	11.1 / 12.0	20.3 / 20.8	15.3 / 15.9	437.616
DeepLabV3+	ResNet34	83.3 / 82.6	90.7 / 90.2	90.7 / 90.5	91.0 / 90.2	84.1 / 83.5	11.8 / 13.0	25.3 / 26.1	19.4 / 19.8	126.801
FPN	ResNet34	80.6 / 80.3	88.8 / 88.7	89.7 / 89.1	88.5 / 88.5	81.6 / 81.3	10.1 / 11.9	20.9 / 21.6	16.5 / 17.1	110.005
PSPNet	ResNet34	75.5 / 75.3	85.4 / 85.2	87.4 / 86.8	84.0 / 84.1	76.7 / 76.5	5.3 / 6.6	14.7 / 15.3	11.0 / 11.4	37.735
LinkNet	ResNet34	82.8 / 82.5	90.3 / 90.1	90.7 / 90.5	90.2 / 90.0	83.8 / 83.4	2.9 / 3.7	27.0 / 27.5	21.8 / 22.2	87.589
MAnet	ResNet34	84.8 / 84.1	91.5 / 91.0	91.6 / 91.1	91.7 / 91.5	85.7 / 84.9	11.3 / 13.5	31.1 / 31.5	25.3 / 25.6	133.689
U-Net	ResNet50	84.6 / 83.9	91.4 / 90.9	91.8 / 91.3	91.4 / 91.0	85.6 / 84.8	13.7 / 14.3	31.3 / 31.6	25.4 / 25.7	171.310
U-Net	MobileNetV2	81.7 / 81.2	89.6 / 89.2	90.7 / 89.7	88.9 / 89.4	82.7 / 81.9	6.9 / 7.7	27.6 / 27.7	22.5 / 22.5	54.339
U-Net	DenseNet121	84.8 / 84.1	91.5 / 91.0	92.1 / 91.8	91.2 / 90.8	85.7 / 84.8	10.3 / 13.4	30.8 / 31.6	25.4 / 26.0	135.825
U-Net	EfficientNet-B0	83.8 / 83.3	90.9 / 90.6	91.2 / 90.9	91.0 / 90.7	84.8 / 84.1	7.2 / 8.6	29.7 / 30.1	24.0 / 24.1	40.530
U-Net	ConvNeXt-Base	84.6 / 84.2	91.4 / 91.2	91.1 / 91.2	92.0 / 91.5	85.5 / 85.0	10.7 / 14.5	31.2 / 31.7	25.2 / 25.6	61.305
U-Net	ViT-B/16	84.3 / 83.7	91.2 / 90.8	91.3 / 90.8	91.5 / 91.2	85.2 / 84.5	13.5 / 14.5	29.8 / 30.2	24.6 / 24.8	53.708
U-Net	Swin-Base	84.1 / 83.4	91.1 / 90.7	91.5 / 91.1	91.0 / 90.6	85.0 / 84.3	11.7 / 14.4	29.6 / 29.9	24.5 / 24.6	73.948
U-Net	LeViT-128s	73.9 / 74.6	84.2 / 84.7	85.6 / 86.6	83.7 / 83.6	74.9 / 75.5	2.2 / 2.7	21.5 / 21.8	17.1 / 17.2	47.576
U-Net	MiT-B0	86.0 / 85.3	92.2 / 91.8	92.2 / 92.3	92.4 / 91.6	86.8 / 86.1	16.6 / 17.8	32.0 / 32.3	26.0 / 26.1	46.814
U-Net	MiT-B1	86.6 / 86.2	92.6 / 92.3	92.8 / 92.7	92.6 / 92.3	87.4 / 86.9	16.3 / 17.9	33.8 / 34.5	27.4 / 28.0	77.915
U-Net	MiT-B2	87.0 / 86.6	92.8 / 92.6	93.3 / 93.3	92.5 / 92.2	87.8 / 87.2	20.6 / 20.3	34.1 / 34.9	27.7 / 28.3	109.874
U-Net	MiT-B3	87.3 / 86.8	93.1 / 92.7	93.4 / 93.1	92.9 / 92.6	88.1 / 87.4	25.4 / 25.1	35.0 / 35.7	28.5 / 29.0	168.322
U-Net	MiT-B4	87.2 / 87.1	92.9 / 92.9	93.1 / 92.9	93.0 / 93.2	87.9 / 87.7	24.8 / 24.0	35.4 / 36.2	28.7 / 29.4	224.405
U-Net	MiT-B5	87.2 / 87.1	93.0 / 92.9	93.2 / 93.2	93.0 / 92.9	88.0 / 87.7	25.5 / 25.8	35.3 / 36.2	28.6 / 29.3	281.599

option (37.74G) but with reduced accuracy.

d) *Cross-resolution trends.*: Increasing input resolution improves absolute scores across architectures. Transformer backbones (MiT) scale favorably compared to CNNs, maintaining good IoU/Dice and thin-structure metrics (TS-IoU, Boundary-F1, Skeleton Similarity). Precision vs. recall trade-offs persist: MiT-B3 favors precision, while MiT-B4/B5 emphasize recall and boundary fidelity. CPR values are lower than pixel metrics, reflecting the difficulty of preserving topology; they improve with stronger backbones and higher resolution.

C. Notes on Efficiency

The table reports theoretical FLOPs to characterize computational cost. While device-specific throughput (FPS), memory, and power depend on implementation and hardware, the FLOPs trends indicate accuracy–efficiency trade-offs useful for embedded selection.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Application-Oriented Guidance

Based on the multi-resolution evaluation in Tables I–III:

Accuracy-focused: U-Net + MiT-B4 provides good overall performance at 256×256 and 512×512, and remains competitive at 1024×1024.

Precision-oriented: Consider U-Net + MiT-B3 when precision is prioritized (e.g., 512×512 validation precision 91.7%), or U-Net + MiT-B5 for high-precision applications at 512×512.

Compute-constrained: PSPNet offers the lowest FLOPs at all scales but with reduced accuracy; LinkNet and FPN provide more balanced options; MobileNetV2 backbones are suitable for tight budgets with moderate accuracy. EfficientNet-B0

and MiT-B0 deliver better accuracy–efficiency trade-offs than PSPNet at 256×256.

B. Thin Structure Detection

TS-IoU and skeleton similarity metrics reveal that fine branch detection remains challenging across all architectures. At 256×256, the best-performing model achieves 76% TS-IoU, indicating room for improvement in sub-pixel structure preservation. Potential enhancement strategies include:

- Multi-scale training with resolution augmentation
- Topology-aware loss functions incorporating connectivity constraints
- Post-processing refinement using morphological operations
- Ensemble methods combining predictions across multiple scales

C. Deployment Considerations

For autonomous forestry applications, we recommend a multi-layered approach: (i) conservative detection thresholds optimized for good recall to reduce missed branches, (ii) temporal consistency validation across video sequences to reduce false positives, and (iii) human oversight integration for high-risk scenarios. The reported per-frame metrics provide baselines that should be validated under real-world operational conditions including variable lighting, motion blur, and diverse environmental contexts.

D. Study Limitations

This study has limitations that indicate future research directions:

- Dataset diversity limited to urban tree species; extension to forest environments needed
- Evaluation focused on static imagery; motion blur and dynamic lighting effects require investigation
- Efficiency assessed via theoretical FLOPs; device-level throughput, memory, and power measurements are needed
- Performance assessment based on controlled conditions; real-world validation needed for deployment

VI. CONCLUSION

We benchmarked tree branch segmentation at 256×256 , 512×512 , and 1024×1024 on the Urban Street Tree Dataset [7], evaluating CNN and transformer architectures. Beyond IoU/Dice, we assessed TS-IoU, CPR, boundary-F1, and skeleton similarity to capture thin-structure preservation and topology. U-Net with MiT-B4 performs well at lower/mid resolutions; at 1024×1024 , MiT-B3/B4/B5 are competitive depending on precision–recall and boundary quality. Transformer backbones outperform CNNs but incur higher compute; model choices reflect accuracy–efficiency trade-offs for embedded use. Future work includes resolution-agnostic or multi-scale training, topology-aware losses, and real-world validation. These baselines support systematic comparison and inform autonomous forestry system design.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the creators of the Urban Street Tree Dataset and reviewers for their feedback.

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